

The Common Infrared Photodiode as a Radioactive-Particle Sensor

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Principle of Operation

The pertinent Experimental Investigations concern how the Crucial Features (Shape, Slope) of the Graph of the p-i-n Si-Photodiode Detection Photocurrent (I) evolving versus the impinging Infrared ($\lambda=780\text{nm}$) Photonic Flux (Φ) are parametrically affected by the each-time Absorbed Cumulative Dose (δ , in $\#/cm^2$) of Ambient Radioactive Particles (α , β).

Producing successively the above I - Φ Characteristic for Adequate Values of Absorbed Total Radioactive Dose (δ) allows for comparing each of them to the (prior to any Radioactivity-Exposure) Initial one: Thus, monitoring the I - Φ Characteristic's Morphology and (per-Branch) Slope, $\kappa(\delta)$, versus δ can be achieved. Consequently, such a Scheme leads to the Common Photodiode becoming an Indirect Sensor both detecting Ambient-Radioactivity Existence and extracting the Value of a circumstantial Radioactive-Particle Cumulative Dose, δ , by virtue of a (Consecutively Informed) Intelligent Algorithm dynamically processing the respective Characteristic's Data $\{(\Phi, I)|\delta\}$ and Interpolation-wise taking into account the (Expanding Library of) already Saved Cases.

Indicative Experimental Parametric Graph

A Seed Research Article

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